

An updated checklist of earwigs (Insecta: Dermaptera) from Himachal Pradesh, India with new distributional records

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Abstract

The present paper deals with an updated checklist of 37 species from 16 genera and 5 families of Dermaptera from Himachal Pradesh. The study revealed three species, viz. *Nala basalis* Bey-Bienko, 1970, *Hypergus humeralis* (Kirby, 1891) and *Forficula tawangensis* Srivastava, 1984 are recorded for the first time from Himachal Pradesh.

Keywords: Earwigs, Dermaptera, New Record, Himachal Pradesh, India, Checklist.

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Introduction

Dermaptera is an insect order, comprising of relatively small, primitive group of free living insects, commonly known as "earwigs". The main characteristic feature of Dermaptera is the presence of a pair of unsegmented cerci at the posterior end of the abdomen. The cerci serve a variety of functions including prey capture, defence and possibly in sexual selection (Burr, 1910; Haas and Kukalova-Peck, 2001). Dermaptera are recorded from all over the world and are abundant in tropical countries than other regions.

The order Dermaptera is represented by 1942 species globally (Hopkins *et al.*, 2017). Of which, 284 species belonging to 72 genera and 7 families are recorded from India (Srivastava, 1988, 2003, 2013). From the Indian Himalayan region, 152 species belonging to 52 genera and 7 families are recorded (Deepak and Ghosh, 2018).

Previously, many workers contributed to the Dermaptera fauna of Himachal Pradesh. The major work done by Burr (1910), Hebard (1923), Baijal and Singh (1954), Singh (1955), Kapoor (1966, 1968, 1974), Srivastava and Lal (1992) and Srivastava (1988, 1995, 2003, 2005, 2013) reported 34 species of Dermaptera from Himachal Pradesh. Present study reports three more additional records of species from the state

and at present a total of 37 species are known.

The present study attempts to update the distribution status of three newly recorded Dermaptera species from Himachal Pradesh and discuss their details. Along with a brief description of the new records from the state, an updated checklist of 37 species under 16 genera and 5 families of Dermaptera from Himachal Pradesh is provided.

Materials and Methods

The Dermaptera specimens collected from Himachal Pradesh by different researchers during surveys conducted in 2012 and 2014, available in the Head Quarters of Zoological Survey of India, Kolkata and some other backlog collections were studied for the present work.

The specimens were sorted out, pinned and identified based on their morphological characters and structure of male genitalia, following Srivastava (1988, 2003 & 2013). The male genitalia were extracted and mounted on a slide. The specimens and genitalia were studied with the help of a Stereo Zoom Binocular Microscope. All identified specimens were registered and deposited in National Zoological Collection of Zoological Survey of India, Kolkata.

An updated checklist of earwigs from Himachal Pradesh, India

Figure 1. Map of Himachal Pradesh showing collection localities.

Results

Taxonomic Account / Systematic Account

Superfamily- Anisolaboidea Sakai, 1982

Family- Labiduridae Verhoeff, 1902

Subfamily- Nalinae Steinmann, 1975

Genus- *Nala* Zacher, 1910

The genus *Nala* is distributed in Africa and Oriental Regions. In India, there are three known species, of which *N. nepalensis* and *N. basalis* are montane species of Oriental Region, whereas, *N. lividipes* is a worldwide distributed species.

1. *Nala basalis* Bey-Bienko, 1970

Material examined: India: Himachal Pradesh: Mandi Dist. (31.84638N, 76.85027E), 02.ii.1965, 1♂, Reg no. 39231/H5, coll: A. Husain; India: Himachal Pradesh: Solan Dist.: Giripool (30.88166N, 77.21000E), 06.x.2012, 1♂, Reg no. 38815/H5, coll: A. Raha & party.

Diagnosis: *N. basalis* is differentiated from other two species by the shapes; base with or without short depressed tooth internally, afterwards branches finely serrated (*N. lividipes*

with forceps long, cylindrical, curved without tooth at base; *N. nepalensis*- basal 1/3rd to 1/2 of forceps dilated internally).

Distribution: India: Himachal Pradesh (present record), Manipur and Mizoram.

Elsewhere: East Afghanistan, Pakistan, Thailand.

Superfamily- Forficuloidea Tillyard, 1926

Family- Forficulidae Stephens, 1829

Subfamily- Opisthocosmiinae Verhoeff, 1902

Genus- *Hypergus* Burr, 1907

The genus *Hypergus* is distributed in Oriental and Ethiopian Regions. Four species are known from Oriental Regions, of which *H. humeralis* is the only species reported from India.

2. *Hypergus humeralis* (Kirby, 1891)

Material examined: India: Himachal Pradesh: Kangra Dist.: Dharmashala (32.23111N, 76.32166E), 15.vii.2014, 1♂ and 9♀, Reg no. 37021/H5, coll. V.D. Hegde & party; India: Himachal Pradesh: Kangra Dist.: Shahpur (32.22527N, 76.53472E, 743m), 14.vii.2014, 2♂ and 4♀, Reg no. 37022/H5, coll. V.D. Hegde & party.

Diagnosis: Blackish to orange brown in colour; elytra black, with an elongated yellow band extending from shoulder to middle; wings yellow with a blackish brown band running along the entire length, tip yellow; abdomen slightly enlarged in the middle, ultimate tergite transverse, sloping and narrowed backwards.

Distribution: India: Himachal Pradesh (present record), Assam, Andaman and Nicobar Islands, Chhattisgarh, Kerala, Madhya Pradesh, Manipur, Meghalaya, Odisha, Uttarakhand, West Bengal.

Elsewhere: Nepal, Sri Lanka, Myanmar, China (Yunnan), Thailand, Vietnam.

Subfamily- Forficulinae Burr, 1907

Genus *Forficula* Linnaeus, 1758

The genus *Forficula* is one of the largest genera, with 25 species known within Indian limits of Himalaya, hills of North East India and in Western Ghats. The genus is distributed in Europe, Africa and Asia, mainly in Palearctic Region.

3. **Forficula tawangensis* Srivastava, 1984

Material examined: India: Himachal Pradesh: Kinnaur Dist.: Sangla (31.42500N, 78.26500E), 30.viii.1976, 1♀, Reg no. 38819/H5, coll. R. Tilak & party.

Diagnosis: Branches of forceps stout, externally concave and internally dilated at basal half or more with its internal margin crenulate,

afterwards strongly incurved, cylindrical, tapering apically with tips pointed.

Distribution: India: Himachal Pradesh (present record), Arunachal Pradesh, Assam, Sikkim and West Bengal.

Remarks: This species is endemic to India.

Discussion

The present study newly added 3 species of Dermaptera, viz., *Nala basalis*, *Hypergus humeralis* and *Forficula tawangensis* to the Himachal Pradesh state. Through this study, a total of 37 species under 16 genera and 5 families are reported. The genus *Forficula* is the most dominant genus with (7 species), followed by the genus *Haplodiplatys* with (5 sp.), *Euborellia* (4 sp.), *Isolaboides*, *Nala* and *Forcipula* with (3 sp.) each.

Of the 5 families reported, Forficulidae with 14 species and 2 new records is the most dominant family, followed by families Anisolabididae & Labiduridae with 7 species each and one new record, followed by Pygidicranidae with 5 species and Chelisochidae with 2 species.

This study also reported the following 6 species *Isolaboides immisi* (Burr), *Forficula asketi* Purohit et al., *F. choprai* Srivastava, *Haplodiplatys glenis* (Kapoor), *H. srivastavi* (Kapoor) and *H. simlaensis* (Kapoor) endemic to Himachal Pradesh.

Figure 2. Generic and species diversity of Dermaptera in Himachal Pradesh, India.

Figures 3-6: 3. *Hypergus humeralis* (Kirby, 1891), ♂; 4. *Hypergus humeralis* (Kirby, 1891), ♀; 5. *Forficula tawangensis* Srivastava, 1984, ♀; 6. *Nala basalis* Bey-Bienko, 1970, ♂.

An Annotated Checklist of Earwigs (Insecta: Dermaptera) From Himachal Pradesh, India

Superfamily- Pygidicranoidea Bruce, Melander & Carpenter, 1954

Family- Pygidicranidae Verhoeff, 1902

Subfamily- Diplatyinae Verhoeff, 1902

Genus- ***Diplatys* Serville, 1831**

1. *Diplatys sinuatus* Hincks, 1955

Genus- ***Haplodiplatys* Hincks, 1955**

2. *Haplodiplatys chinensis* (Hincks, 1954)

3. *Haplodiplatys glenis* (Kapoor, 1968)

4. *Haplodiplatys rufescens* (Kirby, 1986)

5. *Haplodiplatys simlaensis* (Kapoor, 1968)

6. *Haplodiplatys srivastavi* (Kapoor, 1974)

Superfamily- Anisolaboidea Sakai, 1982

Family- Anisolabididae Verhoeff, 1902

Subfamily- Anisolabidinae Verhoeff, 1902

Genus- ***Aborolabis* Srivastava, 1969**

7. *Aborolabis pervicina* (Burr, 1913)

Genus- ***Euborellia* Burr, 1910**

8. *Euborellia annulipes* (Lucas, 1847)

9. *Euborellia compressa* (Borelli, 1907)

10. *Euborellia nainitalensis* Lal, 2012

11. *Euborellia rajasthanensis* Sivastava, 1977

Subfamily- Isolabidinae Brindle, 1978

Genus- ***Isolaboides* Hincks, 1958**

12. *Isolaboides burri* (Borelli, 1909)

13. *Isolaboides elegans* (Hebard, 1917)

14. *Isolaboides immsi* (Burr, 1913)

Family- Labiduridae Verhoeff, 1902

Subfamily- Nalinae Steinmann, 1975

Genus- ***Nala* Zacher, 1910**

15. **Nala basalis* Bey-Bienko, 1970

16. *Nala lividipes* (Dufour, 1829)

17. *Nala nepalensis* (Burr, 1907)

Subfamily- Labidurinae Burr, 1909

Genus- ***Labidura* Leach, 1815**

18. *Labidura riparia* (Pallas, 1773)

Genus- ***Forcipula* Bolivar, 1897**

19. *Forcipula indica* Brindle, 1966

20. *Forcipula quadrispinosa* (Dohrn, 1863)

21. *Forcipula trispinosa* (Dohrn, 1863)

Superfamily- Forficuloidea Tillyard, 1926

Family- Chelisochidae Burr, 1907

Subfamily- Chelisochinae Burr, 1907

Genus- ***Hamaxas* Burr, 1907**

22. *Hamaxas melanocephalus* (Dohrn, 1865)

Genus- ***Proreus* Burr, 1907**

23. *Proreus decipiens* (Kirby, 1891)

Family- Forficulidae Stephens, 1829

Subfamily- Opisthocosmiinae Verhoeff, 1902

Genus- ***Hypergus* Burr, 1907**

24. **Hypergus humeralis* (Kirby, 1891)

- Subfamily- Allodahliinae Verhoeff, 1902
Genus- **Allodahlia Verhoeff, 1902**
25. *Allodahlia macropyga* (Westwood, 1839)
26. *Allodahlia coriacea* (Bormans, 1894)
- Subfamily- Anechurinae Verhoeff, 1902
Genus- **Anechura Scudder, 1876**
27. *Anechura stoliczkae* Burr, 1911
28. *Anechura zubovskii* Semenov, 1901
- Subfamily- Eudohrniinae Burr, 1907
Genus- **Eudohrnia Burr, 1907**
29. *Eudohrnia metallica* (Dohrn, 1865)
- Subfamily- Forficulinae Burr, 1907
Genus- **Elaunon Burr, 1907**
30. *Elaunon bipartitus* (Kirby, 1891)
Genus- **Forficula Linnaeus, 1758**
31. *Forficula asketi* Purohit, Julka and Lal, 1985
32. *Forficula beelzebub* (Burr, 1900)
33. *Forficula choprai* Srivastava, 2013
34. *Forficula davidi* Burr, 1905
35. *Forficula planicollis* Kirby, 1891
36. *Forficula schlagintweiti* (Burr, 1904)
37. * *Forficula tawangensis* Srivastava, 1984
*New Additional Record
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- References**
Baijal, H.N. and Singh, S. 1954. Entomological Survey of the Himalayas Part III: On a collection of Dermaptera. Agra University Journal of Research Science 3(2): 455-462.
Burr, M. 1910. Fauna of British India, including Ceylon and Burma. Dermaptera: xviii + 1-127.
Deepak C.K. and Ghosh D. 2018. Insecta: Dermaptera. In: K. Chandra, D. Gupta, K.C. Gopi, B. Tripathy, and V. Kumar, (eds.). Faunal Diversity of Indian Himalaya. Kolkata: Zoological Survey of India. pp. 265-272.
Haas, F. and Kukalova-Peck, J. 2001. Dermaptera hindwing structure and folding, new evidence for superordinal relationship within Neoptera (Insecta). European Journal of Entomology 98: 445-509.
Hebard, M. 1923. Studies in Indian Dermaptera. Memoires of Department of Agriculture in India Entomology Series 7: 195-242.
Hopkins, Heidi, Maehr, M.D., Haas, F. and Deem, L.S. 2017. Dermaptera Species File. Version 5.0/5.0. [25/07/2017]
Kapoor, V.C. 1966. Three new species of Dermaptera from North West Himalayas. Annals and Magazine of Natural History 9(13): 389-387.
Kapoor, V.C. 1968. Studies on some Indian Dermaptera. Entomologist 101: 80-82.
Kapoor, V.C. 1974. *Genitalata mahajani* gen. et sp. nov. from Himachal Pradesh, India (Dermaptera: Chelisochidae). Zoological Journal of the Linnean Society 55(1): 83-86.
Singh, S. 1955. Entomological Survey of the Himalayas Part VIIA. Collection of Dermaptera. Agra University Journal of Research Science 4(1): 179-186.
Srivastava, G.K. 1988. Fauna of India and the adjacent countries, Dermaptera, Part-I, Superfamily: Pygidicranoidea. Calcutta: Zoological Survey of India. I -xii + 1-268.
Srivastava, G.K. 1995. Insecta: Dermaptera. In: Fauna of Western Himalaya (U.P). Himalayan Ecosystem Series, 3. Kolkata: Zoological Survey of India. pp. 43-45.
Srivastava, G.K. 2003. The Fauna of India and the adjacent countries, Dermaptera (Part-2): (Superfamily: Anisolaboidae). Kolkata: Zoological Survey of India. 235 pp.
Srivastava, G.K. 2005. Insecta: Dermaptera. In: Fauna of Western Himalaya, Himachal Pradesh, 2(2004). Kolkata: Zoological Survey of India. pp. 103-110.
Srivastava, G.K. 2013. Fauna of India and the adjacent Countries, Dermaptera: Apachyoidae and Forficuloidae, Part III. Kolkata: Zoological Survey of India. 469 pp.
Srivastava, G.K. and Lal, B. 1992. Studies on some material of Dermaptera from Himachal Pradesh, India. Rec. Zoological Survey of India 91(1): 111-125.